

Investigating the Effects of Partial and Full Redundancy on Multimedia Learning

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Abstract:	Verbal redundancy is the concurrent presentation of text and verbatim speech. Research has shown that redundant presentations can be facilitating or inhibiting to learning depending on how they are presented. Little is known about how the length of text or the degree of redundancy may influence learning outcomes. The present study fills this important gap. The study examined the effects of learning with LongTextFullAudio, ShortTextFullAudio, LongTextPartial Audio, and ShortTextPartialAudio. Participants (N=319) were randomly assigned to study one of four presentations on the development of human memory. The dependent measures were free recall and transfer. Results showed significant differences between groups on free recall but not on transfer. Theoretical and practical implications of the findings are discussed.

Abstract

Verbal redundancy is the concurrent presentation of text and verbatim speech. Research has shown that redundant presentations can be facilitating or inhibiting to learning depending on how they are presented. Little is known about how the length of text or the degree of redundancy may influence learning outcomes. The present study fills this important gap. The study examined the effects of learning with *LongTextFullAudio*, *ShortTextFullAudio*, *LongTextPartial Audio*, and *ShortTextPartialAudio*. Participants ($N=319$) were randomly assigned to study one of four presentations on the development of human memory. The dependent measures were free recall and transfer. Results showed significant differences between groups on free recall but not on transfer. Theoretical and practical implications of the findings are discussed.

Keywords: multimedia learning, redundancy, cognitive load, interest, audio, text

Objectives

Verbal redundancy results from the concurrent presentation of text and verbatim speech. Although there is an overwhelming research evidence showing that verbally redundant (audio-text) presentations are better for learning than spoken only presentations (Adesope & Nesbit, 2012), little is known about how the length of text or the degree of redundancy may influence learning outcomes. A primary objective of the present study is to extend the verbal redundancy literature and explore the conditions under which different levels of redundancy or correspondence between the written text and the audio (i.e. partial vs. full redundancy) and different lengths of text (i.e., short text vs. long text) may either optimize or hinder student learning.

More specifically, the present study seeks to understand the effects of learning with four different multimedia materials: (a) long text with a fully redundant audio narration; (b) short text with a full redundant audio narration; (c) long text with partial audio redundancy; and (d) short text with a partially redundant audio narration.

The study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the effects of learning from different levels of redundant materials?
2. How does the length of text influence learning from redundant materials?

Theoretical Framework

Cognitive Load Theory

One of the primary theories guiding multimedia research is the Cognitive Load Theory. This theory posits that working memory is limited in both capacity and duration. Based on this

knowledge, instructional design can help or hinder the learning process (Kalyuga & Sweller, 2014). According to this theory, there are three types of cognitive load (CL), which are additive in nature. The first is intrinsic load which describes the inherent nature of the learning materials and the degree of complexity. The next two types of cognitive load include extraneous CL and germane CL. Both of these are the target of instructional design, where the goal is to decrease extraneous CL and increase germane CL (Kirschner, 2002). Each will be discussed further in the context of the redundancy principle described below.

Redundancy Principle

The redundancy principle of multimedia learning describes that redundancy may take one of two forms including 1) where the information is simultaneously presented in two different modes or 2) where any unnecessary elaboration of the essential material is considered redundant (Kalyuga & Sweller, 2014). The redundancy effect takes place when learners must use their limited working memory capacity to coordinate information from multiple sources, thus increasing extraneous CL. For the redundancy principle to be applicable, there must be complex materials with high levels of intrinsic load where it may be difficult for some learners to determine what is essential to the learning goals. The principle suggests that redundant materials unnecessarily increase extraneous CL and therefore the remaining germane CL is insufficient to process information into long-term schemas for later recall and use.

The redundancy effect can be applied to multiple modes of information including graphics, animations, text and audio, but the focus of this paper is primarily on written/spoken text redundancy due to its frequency of use particularly in higher education. In a meta-analysis of verbal redundancy (i.e. concurrent presentation of text and verbatim speech), Adesope and Nesbit (2012) found that verbally redundant presentations were more beneficial for learning than

spoken-only presentations. To date, the majority of evidence regarding the redundancy effect has primarily focused on two comparison conditions: redundant and non-redundant information. Little is known about how the length of text or the degree of redundancy may influence learning outcomes.

Mixed findings. There is a considerable amount of mixed findings regarding the redundancy effect. While the Cognitive Load Theory suggests that redundant text is harmful for learning outcomes, Moreno and Mayer (2002) found that students had better learning outcomes when they received the materials both in auditory and visual formats than with auditory alone. One explanation for this discrepancy is that individuals may be aided by receiving the information from two different processing channels (Mayer, 2002, 2003).

Boundary Conditions. The contradictory findings in the literature point to a need to understand the conditions under which the redundancy effects are helpful and/or deleterious for learning. Kalyuga and Sweller (2014) summed it up by stating that, “information that is redundant under one set of circumstances is essential under another, and information that is redundant for one person may be essential for another” (p. 259). In our meta-analysis of verbal redundancy (Adesope & Nesbit, 2012), we examined 57 independent studies as well as different moderators of the effects of spoken-only, written-only, and spoken-written conditions. Results showed that redundant materials were more effective than spoken-only materials for low prior knowledge learners, system-paced learning materials, and materials without pictures. Yeung and colleagues (1998) also presented a series of studies which highlighted the need to understand specific conditions that support or hinder students’ learning. Specifically, Yeung et al. (1998) found that redundant presentations supported learning for those with high-expertise, but hindered learning for those where the information was novel.

Although researchers recognize the importance of understanding different moderators of redundancy effects, little is known about (a) the extent of redundancy between the two modes and (b) the length of the text in the materials. Mayer and Johnson (2008) found that the redundant group that studied with short phrases alongside a diagram actually outperformed the non-redundant group suggesting that not all forms of redundancy may require excess extraneous processing.

Method

Participants and Research Design

Three hundred and nineteen participants enrolled in a Developmental course in a large public university in the Northwest of the United States participated in this study. Participants were randomly assigned to one of four groups, investigating the effects of length of redundancy (long vs short) and degree of redundancy (full vs. partial) on learning. Eighty-two participants were randomly assigned to the *LongTextFullAudio* group, 67 to the *LongTextPartialAudio* group, 83 to the *ShortTextFullAudio* group, and 87 to the *ShortTextPartialAudio* group. Students participated in this study during their normal class period. The experiment was conducted in a large classroom with each participant seated in front of a laptop and wearing headphones. The experiment took place individually with each participant attending one session lasting approximately 50 minutes. All the materials were administered online.

2.2. Learning materials and apparatus

The learning materials for this study consisted of four different computer-based PowerPoint presentations on the development of human memory from infancy to adulthood and recall of information (862 words). The presentations differed with respect to both the length of

redundancy (long vs short) and degree of redundancy (full vs. partial) of the learning materials. Each presentation included a spoken narration that was a recording of a human voice reading the same passage displayed in the text conditions. This presentation consisted of 14 individual slides that lasted a little over 6 minutes. The slides advanced automatically after each audio narration for the slide was complete, thus averaging approximately 26 seconds per slide. The presentations allowed transitions between the slides to be controlled by clicking on “Advance to the next slide” and “Return to the previous slide” buttons. Participants viewed all materials on laptop computers equipped with headphones.

2.3. Measures

The dependent variables were the scores on free recall and transfer tests. A free recall test was used to assess participants’ retention of ideas in the passage. After presentation of the material, participants were instructed to write down all they could remember in the passage using a web-based text field. The transfer test consisted of one question that assessed participants’ ability to apply what they learned in the passage to a different context. Participants’ responses on the free recall, transfer, and knowledge tests were collected and recorded electronically.

2.4. Scoring

Prior knowledge of memory and recall of information was assessed by using a pretest that asked participants to list 5 things they knew about memory and learning based on their prior knowledge. The pretest was scored out of 5 points, a point for each listed correct information about memory.

Responses from the free recall test were assessed with a conventional proposition scoring method (Nesbit & Adesope, 2011; Rewey, Dansereau, Skaggs, Hall, & Pitre, 1989). We analyzed the original passage into propositional statements that were approximately equivalent in

meaning to the original passage. Researcher who were blind to the experimental conditions assigned a score from 0 or 1 for each proposition recalled by the participants: 0 points if the proposition was absent or completely inaccurate; 1 point if the proposition was present and completely accurate. Each participant's free recall score was the sum of the proposition scores. We standardized the free recall scores considering the differences in the number of words across the different learning materials.

The transfer test assessed deep understanding of the presentation, particularly the participants' ability to apply the newly acquired knowledge to a different context. When answered correctly, participants received a total of 3 points for the transfer question.

Results

Prior to data analysis and testing the hypotheses, all variables were examined for accuracy of data entry, outliers, and normality of distributions. Data was eliminated for participants who did not spend at least five minutes to study the learning materials and at least one minute to complete each of the free recall and transfer tests. Because the four experimental groups differed significantly in their prior knowledge of the human memory, $F(3,303)=15.59$, $MSE=19.86$, $p<.001$, $\eta^2_p=.134$, a decision was made to use the pretest score as a covariate in subsequent analyses.

Table 1 shows the mean free recall scores, standard deviations and sample sizes for each treatment group. ANCOVA was conducted to compare the effect of presentation on free recall scores in *LongTextFullAudio*, *ShortTextFullAudio*, *LongTextPartialAudio*, and *ShortTextPartialAudio* conditions. ANCOVA using the pretest as the covariate detected an effect due to treatment $F(3,303)=21.05$, $p<.001$, $\eta^2_p=.173$, indicating that 17% of free recall variance

could be attributed to treatment. Bonferroni-adjusted multiple comparisons found differences for *ShortTextPartialAudio* vs. *ShortTextFullAudio* ($d = .85, p < .001$), *ShortTextPartialAudio* vs. *LongTextFullAudio* ($d=1.11, p < .001$), *ShortTextPartialAudio* vs. *LongTextPartialAudio* ($d=.54, p=.001$), and *LongTextPartialAudio* vs. *LongTextFullAudio* ($d=.62, p=.004$). Table 2 shows the mean transfer scores, standard deviations and sample sizes for each treatment group. NCOVA using the pretest as the covariate did not detect an effect due to treatment, $F(3, 303)=.91, p > .05$.

Scholarly Significance

Results showed that on a test of free recall, partially redundant presentations produced significant learning (retention) benefits than fully redundant presentations regardless of whether the text was long or short. This is in line with more recent findings in verbal redundancy and multimedia learning studies (Adesope & Nesbit, 2012; Mayer & Johnson, 2008). Conversely, results showed that on a test of transfer, in comparison with full presentations, partial presentations did not offer statistically and educationally significant learning benefits. This is contrary to the literature that the redundancy effect impairs learning (Kalyuga & Sweller, 2014). The finding is interesting because we anticipated that the partial conditions, particularly the *ShortTextPartialAudio* condition, would help reduce extraneous cognitive load experienced by the learners, allowing them to better integrate the incoming information from both the verbal and visual sources thus leading to higher post-test scores. It is likely that the lack of significant differences among the groups may also be due to the lack of enough variance within the transfer scores, considering that there was only one transfer question with maximum 3 points. It may be that with more transfer questions included, we would have seen sufficient variances to detect a significant effect.

This study offers evidence that the redundancy principle does not simply occur when information is presented in two modes simultaneously, rather it is necessary to consider the complexity of the given task, as well as the learner's prior knowledge. A high-prior knowledge learner is less likely to experience the redundancy effect as compared to a low-prior knowledge learner who on the other hand may struggle to identify and integrate key information for later recall. In order to provide instructional designs that are beneficial to both high- and low-prior knowledge learners, researchers should further investigate redundancy effect using different combination of the modes of presentation, in different content areas, with students of differing prior knowledge and with more robust dependent measures.

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TABLE 1.

Free Recall Performance of the Four Treatment Groups

Treatment	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>
<i>LongTextFullAudio</i>	11.45	5.15	82
<i>LongTextPartialAudio</i>	14.96	6.26	65
<i>ShortTextFullAudio</i>	13.28	4.83	79
<i>ShortTextPartialAudio</i>	18.91	7.98	81

TABLE 2

Transfer Performance of the Four Treatment Groups

Treatment	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>
<i>LongTextFullAudio</i>	1.98	.69	82
<i>LongTextPartialAudio</i>	2.08	.74	66
<i>ShortTextFullAudio</i>	2.19	.88	79
<i>ShortTextPartialAudio</i>	2.11	.88	81

Appendix A. Learning Materials

Researchers disagree on the age from which memories can be retrieved. Although early research supported the notion of infantile amnesia - the lack of memory for experiences occurring prior to three years of age - more recent research shows that infants do retain memories. However, memories may not be easily, or accurately, retrieved. For example, memories are susceptible to interference from other, newer information, which may displace or block out the older information, thereby preventing its recall.

One reason why infants appear to remember less may be because language plays a key role in determining the way memories from early in life can be recalled: Older children and adults may be able to report memories using only the vocabulary that they had available at the time of the initial event, when the memories were stored. Because their vocabulary at the time of initial storage may have been quite limited, they are unable to describe the event later in life, even though it is actually in their memories.

Memory improves throughout the course of childhood and adolescence. First there are improvements in the basic processes and capacities related to memory. Although there is little evidence to suggest that the capacity of either sensory memory or long-term memory changes during childhood, it does appear that short-term, or working memory does improve with age.

To explain this improvement, developmental psychologist Robbie Case, who is known as a neo-Piagetian theorist, has blended information processing and Piagetian approaches. Case suggests that cognitive development proceeds because of increases in working memory capabilities.

The number of chunks of information that can be held in working memory increase throughout childhood, suggesting an increase in its capacity. But increased capacity does not necessarily imply increased size. Case suggests that observed improvements in working memory are due to increases in the operating efficiency of working memory.

According to the operating efficiency hypothesis, people are able to remember material better with age because they process information more quickly and use more effective, suitable strategies. Memory improvements are not due to increases in the size of working memory. Yet, even though the storage capacity of short-term memory is not expanding with age, less effort is needed to process information, and more cognitive resources are available to store information. The ultimate result is that, with age, more information can be processed in working memory.

The greater efficiency of processing is indicated by increases in speed of processing with age. As individuals become older, they are able to process the same material with greater speed. One important reason is that increases in brain maturation permit the faster manipulation of letters and numbers.

But improvements in the efficiency of processing are not the full story of memory improvement. As we see next, increases in the use of memory control strategies and the growth of metamemory and general knowledge also lead to improvement in memory.

Children's understanding of memory becomes more sophisticated as they grow older and increasingly engage in control strategies – conscious, intentionally used tactics to improve cognitive processing. For instance, school-age children are aware that rehearsal, the repetition of information, is a useful strategy for improving memory, and they increasingly employ it over the course of middle childhood.

Similarly, children progressively make more effort to organize material into coherent patterns, a strategy that permits them to recall it better. For instance, when faced with remembering a list including cups, knives, forks, and plates, older school-age children are more likely to group the items into coherent patterns – cups and plates, forks, and knives – than children just entering the school age.

Children also begin to use strategies that are explicitly taught. For instance, a technique called the keyword strategy can help students learn the vocabulary of a foreign language, the capitals of the state, or other information in which two sets of words or labels are paired. In the keyword strategy, one word is paired with another that sounds like it.

For example, in learning foreign language vocabulary, a foreign word is paired with a common English word that has a similar sound. The English word is the keyword. Thus, to learn the Spanish word for duck (*pato*, pronounced *pot-o*), the keyword might be “pot”; for the Spanish word for horse (*caballo*, pronounced *cob-eye-yo*), the keyword might be “eye.” Once the keyword is chosen, children then form a mental image of the two words interacting with one another. For instance, a student might use an image of a duck taking a bath in a pot to remember the word *pato*, or a horse with bulging eyes to remember the word *caballo*.

In addition to increasingly using explicit strategies as they get older, children also begin to recall memories more frequently in terms of scripts, general representations in memory of a sequence or series of events. For instance, when preschoolers experience the same activity or event repeatedly—such as being driven to preschool five days a week—the activity becomes remembered in terms of a general script. Subsequently, unless something unusual occurs, such as seeing an accident, it is difficult to recall anything specific about any particular ride to school because it is remembered in terms of the general script.